

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.4

0.6

53°56'

12 $z_{\text{sp}}=0.99258$

55'

54'

53'

16^h09^m25^s20^s

15^s

10^s

05^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

100 kpc

